

Ethnographic Study of Third Gender Community at Karachi City of Sindh-Pakistan

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

We humans are habitual of classifying things by nature, we use to set boundaries and circles and classified thing according to our self-established socially built boundaries, our classification is not only for other things but we have classified ourselves too, we human along with all other species are divided into two categories male and female on the basis of our sex by the nature. We have also socially classified ourselves into two categories man and woman, social categories are known as gender assigned by society. But there are many people who don't fit in any of two categories made by both nature and society. This study is all about those marginalized and suppressed people, whom we all consider as an object of amusement and hurl ugly comments to them. Through this study I have tried to analyze and understand the biological and psychological variations which make them different from others, I have tried to explore their internal world, which was hidden earlier, I have lightened their occupations, their living style and their internal social structure along with their religious beliefs, I have changed all real names for the sake of their privacy. I hope this document will help readers to think again about the third gender community and provide guidance for future researchers who they want to explore this extra ordinary sub-society with its unique culture.

Keywords: THIRD GENDER, COMMUNITY, BOUNDRIES, CULTURE.

Introduction

It is an interesting area for anthropologists to study the current human organizations and its problem. In our society gender decides the life patterns of people, your gender will decide that what you will wear, what work will you do, what will be your role and duties and even how you have to talk and behave with genders other than yours. Gender is always based on human sex usually which type of reproductive organs one has male or female that will decide his or her gender, which can determine one's place in a society. But what

about those who didn't fit in any of these categories because they don't have properly developed sexual organs or they want to live like opposite gender and had removed their reproductive organs, these are considered as alternative genders in different cultures we find these gender roles throughout the globe. Here we often saw them with wearing female dresses dancing. Begging at roadsides, we have so many words to call them i.e. Eunuchs, Hermaphrodite, Intersex, Third sex, Third gender, Morat, Zankha, Zanana, Namard, Hijra, Khosra, KhadraFaqeeretc. But we don't know them; this study is a step forward to understand third genders life closely at Karachi City of Sindh-Pakistan. This study has focused on the internal life of these people, what is their perspective about their life? Why people treat them with discriminatory attitudes? How they are satisfied while living their life? What are their economic resources? How difficult is for them to make a living? Where do they live? How they are socially bound with their community? What is their social status in society at present and what was their status in past societies? What do people think about them did they possess any divine power.

Literature Review

For any research it is necessary that before going to do research one should have a look at present work conducted by earlier researchers in the same field of interest Researcher should read literature related with his area of interest. Literature review helped me to understand my research question and set my aim and objectives for this research as I become aware of past researches, I designed my research as to explore facts in new dimensions which are still hidden about third gender community.

Sex and Gender: Term sex is used to show biological differentiation between members of same species, biological organs of person shows that which sex is assigned to him/her either male or female, while term gender is a socially constituted concept which shows that what will be a person's role in society but usually gender is assigned on sexual orientation. According to Esplen and Jolly, (2006; 2) "The term gender has been increasingly used to distinguish between sex as biological and gender as socially constructed". According to Goldstein J, 2003:2"Sex is fixed and based in nature, gender is fluid and based in culture" According to American Psychological Association, 2011"Sex refers to a person's biological status and is typically categorized as male, female or intersex (i.e. typical combinations of features that usually distinguish male from female). There are a number of indicators of biological sex, including sex chromosomes, gonads, internal reproductive organs, and external genitalia. Gender refers to attitudes, feelings; and behavior that a given culture associates with a person's biological sex behavior that is compatible with culture expectations is referred to as gender-normative; behaviors that are viewed as incompatible with these expectations constitute gender non-conformity". From all above statements it is clear that gender is socially developed concept and can be changed, but sex is biologically assigned and fixed category which determined once gender in society. Gender defines that what role society expect from individuals on the basis of their sexual orientation.

Third Gender: Third gender is a term used for those persons who don't fit in any of two male and female

gender categories due to their undefined biological orientation of sexual organs; these are known as hermaphrodite. According to MsBhutta, p.47 “Intersexual/hermaphrodite is a person who may have biological characteristics of both the male and female sexes. In simple words, human beings whose biological sex cannot be classified as clearly male or female are classified as intersexual or hermaphrodite”. This shows that a person is inborn with undefined biological organs that is why he is out of mainstream genders of society, but third gender community is not only constituted of these hermaphrodites but there are other categories of individual which are combined member’s of third gender community, As MsBhutta says, p.48 “Transsexual is an individual who identifies with a physical sex that is different from his biological one”. A person who has desire to live like opposite sex and be accepted as one from his opposite sex, they have strong desire to shape their physical appearance as possible as like their desired opposite sex, they may take surgeries and hormonal treatment to modified their bodies, According to Bhutta, p48 “Transgender is a person who is born with typical male or female anatomies but feel as though he/she has been born into the wrong body”. Pakistani third gender community is constituted upon all these categories and locally knows as khowaja Sara, Murat, Hijra and Khusra.

Third Gender and Islam: Islam is considered complete code of life, which guides its followers in every leap of life Islam has provided guidelines about third gender community. According to Tariq Hashmi, august 2003, “Eunuch will be dealt with according to their apparent traits of gender. If their physical traits relate mostly to male, for example having a beard, they would be considered male and vice versa”. In Islamic society they are considered free from sexual desires for this reason they become most desired guards for the security and maintenance of the tomb of Prophet Muhammad (P.B.U.H), As according to Ahmad Nasr, 2001:173 “Though the prophet passed away it is believed that his body is not corrupted by worms and that he lives in this tomb a Barzakhi life (a life in which time is suspended). The eunuchs Marmon argues are also well suited for serving the prophet’s tomb for they being castrated before adolescence, never go through the changes of puberty and course reproduce. In other words, they live a life in which time is suspended. No wonder then that in a legend about the prophet’s tomb their roles and the role of prepubescent child are exchanged. Thus Marmon gives another reason in addition to the once already enumerate for the appointment of eunuchs to serve the prophet’s tomb, such as their concentration their professions and lack of Shahwa (sexual desire) and therefore their freedom from major ritual impurity”. But in the same chapter Ahmad at another place quoted Marmon again and argued that, “There were sixteen Aghas in medina and fourteen in Mecca in 1948 when I interviewed them (incidentally Marmon gives their number in medina seventeen). When I interviewed one of them, last march 2001, I found that their number diminished to thirteen in medina three passed away in 1986,1996 and 1998 respectively. Their roles including the role of sexual police have also greatly diminished. No eunuch has been appointed since 1984, and in my view non will be in future”. According to Balouch, 2010:49 (Urdu Book) “These are Allah’s creature, and Allah has made them in this way, they are innocent there should be mercy on them, if these people are dumped by their families then government and well settled people should create shelter houses for them, to serve

humanity” . And for inheritance and as well as funeral is concerned Islam also gives clear directions about it as. According to Balouch, 2010:45 (Urdu Book) “If any hermaphrodite dies then his close relative can give him “Ghosal” if there is absence of relative then any one can give him “Tayamum”, Muslims perform his Janaza Nimas and he will be buried in Muslim’s graveyard. If his father died before his death then he is able to inherit half share according guidance present for male inheritance and half share according to guidance for female share in property”.

Impacts of Colonization on Third Gender: In south Asia every corner of society has influence of colonization period, third gender community is also a victim of colonization, before colonization during Muslim period they were at highly respectable jobs and almost all of them was earning with respect but it is British period which throw third genders on roads and they started doing these odd jobs and prostitution for earning bread for their selves, According to Adam, 2011“It’s ironic that a religion of love (Christianity) caused these accepted people to be forced to beg for a living when it overtook India during British occupation” . According to Aitken (Translated by Hussain Badshah, 2006:218“After British conquest they get freedom or thrown at roads without any check and balance, because they were all alone, and helpless so naturally all combined together and started living together”.

Pakistani Third Gender Community: Pakistani third gender community includes hermaphrodites, transsexuals, transvestite, transgender and eunuchs. According to Bhutta, p 48 “in Pakistan Khowaja Saras are living mostly within their own community and own cultural contexts. leading the most challenging lives characterized by discrimination and recurring and pervasive violence. Usually they live in groups of four or five or more as Chelas (disciples) supervised by a Guru (teacher)”.

Appearance of Third Gender Community in Sindh: It is difficult to trace actual orientation of third gender community in Sindh, there are only mythological assumptions made by historians about the presence of third gender community, the only way is to rely upon the stories provided by third gender community itself, According to JunejoTanveer, (Sindhi Book) “According to a story it was Khowaja Nezam-u-din’s follower Ameer Khusroo’s Chela named “Ganga Rami” who first started third gender community in Sindh. He visited Sindh and started making his followers here, and worn them “Byk” (Female Dress) those Faqeer’s were called as “Suhagi Faqeers” they wear ivory bangles in arms, they use to wear yellow and green colored clothes” (Junejo, 2004:216)“About institutionalization of third genders in Sindh we find a myth story from Khairpur, according to a senior guru from Khairpur, about three hundred years ago “SanakanFaqeer” established a Marhi at Hyderabad. Talpur rulers of Sindh treat them with respect and use to give them camels with gold chains and also many other alms”.(Junejo, 2004:217)“Wazirzadas have eight Marhi’s at Karachi, Badshahzadas was having initially an Marhi at PakaQila, but during British era queen Victoria allotted them Marhi at tower market area with the passage of time that Marhi was divided in to three parts and now there are three traditional Marhi’s present in Hyderabad” (Junejo, 2004:218).

Victims of Discrimination: Third gender community faces discrimination everywhere, they all are treated as they are aliens on earth, and discrimination starts from their families and pushes them to leave houses and

join third gender community because there is no other place for a third gender, where he can get shelter, As mentioned by MsBhutta, p50 “According to Khushboo, a Khawaja Sara, “when psychological torture by relatives and their taunting behavior became intolerable I left my house to join a Khawaja Sara group where I felt I had acceptance and more respect as human being”. According to Balouch (2010) “Transvestites are continuously made an object of discrimination in Pakistan. He added that citizens should not label and deride transvestites as sex workers or homosexuals. He emphasized they should not be discriminated against because of their sexual orientation”. According to Maria Amir, (2010) “The theatricality and histrionics, they say, are part necessity and a part amusement. “We are the biggest joke there is but people don’t laugh with us or at us,” says Naji. “They laugh behind our backs.” So we make fun of ourselves and badger all these people in their fancy cars. Who don’t know how lucky they are simply to have born whole”. According to Syed Shamsuddin, (2010) “Pakistani society and law continues to their discriminatory attitudes towards the transvestites. Their “sexual identity” is an essential component of human expression and inherent in the fundamental right to freedom of expression guaranteed under basic human rights and defined in universal declaration of human rights, there for they must be recognized as equal citizens of Pakistan”.

Attitude of Police with Third Gender: Police also don’t consider third genders as equal citizens they use to harass them, beat them and took their money and even rapes them. According to an research briefing, (2009) “Sexual and physical abuse among Bantha and Khotki, and client violence among Khusra, increased the odds of infection. All sex worker groups were exploited by police, who played on their fear of exposure or raids to negotiate bribes of money or free sex. More than a quarter of Khusra had been raped by police in the last year”. According to Sindhe Ujwala Sunil, (2012:3) “The harassment and surveillance by the police has been extends many times into the privacy of their homes. The place with the most scope of abuse is the police station where the police on regular basis, violate all canons of civilized behavior by physical, sexually and verbally abusing and humiliating Hijras and Kothis’.

Statement of Problem

In our society people are divided on the basis of their gender once gender is decided society expect individuals to behave according to requirements of that particular gender. If society finds any one crossing his/ her boundaries awarded by gender he/she will live at the margins of society.

In this research study researcher has documented the various types of third gendered persons, how they are different from main dominating two genders? What are the biological and psychological variations that made them different from others? Research also has paid attention that how those third gendered persons are internally classified and different from each other? And what are the internal boundaries of their sub-culture that allows them to behave in a certain manner and organized their living patterns.

This study has also focused on the behavior of society towards those who lives out of mainstream genders of society they behave like opposite genders, and people become confuse how to deal them? This study have revealed attitudes of people towards the third gender, why do people don’t like to handshake with them, to

eat with them, even to sit with them? Just because of their gender, why they are considered out of humanity, this research study has investigated the belief of people towards third gender, people do consider that they possess divine powers, usually people are afraid of their curse and people often give them alms for good fortune usually on the occasion like at the birth of male child and at the weddings.

Findings and Discussions

This was an Ethnographic research study based upon first hand data collected through participant observation, interviews and direct discussions with third gender community, the study discloses the internal social structure of third gender community, and also explains that how that structure functions for the survival of individual and group life of community, how they are divided into categories on the basis of their biological variations and according to their caste. This research is based upon field work data is collected from Karachi this study represents only third gender community living here, and can be only generalized over Sindh at some extent. But cannot and should not be generalized for whole Pakistan, because third gender community is most mobilized and dynamic community their norms and values are changing with different social settings.

1. Case Study (Gori): I was twenty years old when I come to join this community, when I was a child at school other boys use to call me Baji, in school I always use to play with girls, all my boy fellows use to tease me so finally I left school. My family was very kind with me they allow me to wear female dresses and do household chores with women. In early childhood I started doing sex with other boys of my age, I did play both active and passive role during sex, and slowly I liked being penetrated by other boys. I started doing hair cutting at barber's shop but I didn't like that, I just liked to dance in public and started dancing with Zanas (Transvestites) I liked having sex with other males that is why I do prostitution and earn from that sometimes I thought why didn't God made me female, as I could get married and having children and I could get a respectable place in society, but what to do I would never take operation it is great sin I will live my life as God has created me.

2. Case Study (Kashish): My father died before my birth and my mother joined police force she become busy in earning and feeding us, I use to stay at home with my sisters, I always like to play with my sisters I feel myself as a girl because we have female soul we like to live as female, in childhood my cousin raped me when I was only ten years old. I never told this to any one because my brothers always use to beat me and I thought if I told them they will kill me, slowly I feel pleasure with my cousin, but he was just spoiling me after some days my cousin use to take his friends with him and all of them regularly penetrating me for more than five years, and I do started to visit different people for same purpose. My brothers became aware of my activities they tried to stop me by using force they treated me violently, they burned my feet as I become paralyzed and stay at home but now it was out of my control, at the age of eighteen I started living at my own and joined Faqeer (Bagger) community. I have my own house at Multan (City) I regularly go to visit my family. I have inherited my share from my father's property. I am quite satisfied with my life I consider

myself complete I will never get operation, I am happy as God has created me.

3. Case Study (Gurya): My family knows about me from my childhood, my mother told me that my grandfather's brother was also like me, so I never faced major restriction by family, my mother died in my early age when I was only nine or ten years old. I was younger than all my sisters and brothers I use to play with my sisters and dance on songs, one of our neighbor always play songs and I use to dance, one day when I was moving to my grandmother's house a Pathan neighbor meet me on my way he said me to visit him at evening he has brought an beautiful dress for me I said ok, but at evening I was moving back to my house and suddenly he appeared and took me to his house, he undressed me at time I was only twelve year and rapid me I feel too much pain and become unconscious, after three days when I open my eyes I was at hospital, my sister asked me what happened to me I told them about That Pathan but unfortunately Pathan managed to escape he was from Quetta and living at rented house. After this incident many of my neighbor started to get sexual favor from me and I slowly started liking it.

4. Case Study (Shabnum): I was child when I migrated to Pakistan with my family, when I was child my family forced me to wear male clothes, after the death of my mother and father, my brother use to beat me, so I left my house and started living with Faqeers (baggers). We use to sing and dance at Badhais and people give us something according to their economical conditions, I had never make Chelas, my Guru has given me this house as a gift but I paid fifty thousand for legal documentation. Look there are fake Faqeers (baggers), they use to wear female dresses and take our Badhais, they do prostitution being real Faqeers have gone in a corner. In my life I never allowed any one to take sexual favor from me, this happens with those who they wanted it themselves. My family members tried to stop me from joining Faqeers but I join them because I was born like this, but my family never understands it. They stop talking with me for thirty years, now they come to visit me usually after six months or a year. This is my place I will donate it to Masjid or Madarsa or will give it to anyone who takes care of me when I become ill.

5. Case Study (Salma): I was born like this I am inborn hermaphrodite, I am not Zanana (Transvestite) neither I have take operation and become Narbhan (Emasculated) I possess only one inch tool for urine ejection. I live with my family my mother and father both died in my early age I have two sister and one brother I am elder in my siblings, I took all responsibilities I earn from Badhais, and managed my two sisters wedding and settled down my brother too. I am blood pressure patient I was admitted to civil hospital for fifteen days now they have prescribed me one tablet daily for life time. I never took any female name; I have my N.I.C under my father's name I never joined Faqeer community I have spend my life with my family everyone knows me in neighborhood, if there is any other Faqeer in neighborhood people never give them anything, they all know me and always give their Badhais to me, they all respected me and if any one try to make my fun I can slap them and no one will stop me even their parents didn't say anything to me. I never had any guru or Chela I live in my relatives, I never joined Faqeer's community, some Faqeers save some thing for their old age those who can earn enough to save, majority is like me we have nothing. I have nourished my younger siblings, now they are youngsters and I become old. They are also uneducated, I have

done for them whatever I could do for them now they give me some thing if they have enough from their need, otherwise I have to earn for myself.

6. Case Study (Dilshad): I live with my family for seventeen years then I joined Khadra community, I still have relations with my family, initially they tried to stop me, use to beat me when I was child but now they have accepted me because no I am giving them money, I earn from dance functions, when I was In school, other boys usually touch my hips, sometimes kissed my hands or even hug me and kiss me at lips. Even a teacher who use to teach us computer always touch me here and there, when I was twelve years old one of my friend penetrated me, I feel so good and after that I started having sexual relations with other males. It was my unite wedding day when I first time saw these Murats in full makeup with female clothes, I feel attracted to them and they also realized my intentions and give me their visiting card and next day I went there to meet with them, they treated me very well, and I started going there regularly. They started taking me with themselves at functions where they dance at that time I visit with them in gent's clothes, at first I only look them dancing but slowly and gradually I started dancing with them and I feel so amazed and decided to join their community.

7. Case Study (Naveed): I am living with my family, I am male by birth but my soul is Zanana, initially my family use to beat me and I managed to escape for Punjab. After some time when my elder brother got married and separated from my mother, and there was one for earnings and my mother went ill, then I came back and started working at people's houses, I do household chores like cleaning, washing etc, they paid me monthly. Then my mother and father accepted me they said he is living as he likes but at least he is supporting us it is enough for us. I am living with my family but those Murat's are my friends when ever any one organize dance parties and they ask me to arrange Zanana (Transvestite) dancer I call them and join them at dance or collect money from people. During those programs people abuse touch us at our hips, but I never has faced any kind of serious sexual attack like rape. While I am living with my family so I have social security, my family is a protection for me I didn't have any Guru, and I will never join this community I am happy with my life, God has made me like this and I am satisfied with my life.

8. Case Study (kajri): I am twenty five years old and I joined this field when I was sixteen years old and I am here from nine years, I have studied eighth class in a co-education school I didn't face any discriminatory attitude at school everyone loved me at school. My family is well to do all are educated; I feel shame, so, I never meet my relatives they are all educated. My family still wanted me to come back, but I feel good with my souls my Zanana (Transvestite) sisters, till today I never wear female clothes my family purchased cloths for me, and at functions for dance I wear pant shirts. I was having long hairs my family used to cut them so many time but I again grow them I like long hairs but once my friend throw acid on my hairs and burned them, I lodged F.I.R initially but then I had forgiven him, because he is my first and last love, he was my friend from childhood. When I was fourteen years old we both drunk and he started kissing me as a maid we usually do this, but at that night he wanted to do more and I was also enjoying all that he undressed me, and penetrated me hard initially I felt pain but slowly started enjoying it. Whenever he had

sex with me we both become conscious about what we have done he started crying before me and said me to forgive him as he has hurt me badly.

9. Case Study (Sara): I realized first time in class five that I am different from other boys, before this I was in other school where I was studying with ninety five girls students I was only boy in that class, so I never realized that what is different in me and other boys. I considered myself as girl. But when I come in contact with boys I felt I was not like them. All other boys and even teachers hurl comments on my behavior, and then slowly I learned expected behavior and completed my intermediate. My family treated me as a boy but they told me about my childhood activities, about putting lipstick on my lips, wearing my sister's clothes and fighting with my sisters, I never ever play with boys I liked to stay at home and watch television I like to dance before television, I live about eighteen year with my family and now I am living here from past six years. During those years when I was living as a boy I always managed to visit this Khadra community, but never wanted to join them. But when my friend left me I was having a boyfriend but he also left me and got engaged with a girl, thereafter people tried to get sexual favor from me and I realized that this is what I am so I decided to join this field.

10. Case Study (Ashraf Sayyan): My family accepted me from very beginning my father my brothers all were very caring for me, I have studied till class ninth, in school I never disclose my identity. But things started changing with my father's death I was too young at that time, my mother got married with another man, my step father was very rude with me. First off all he took me out from school, my mother died when I was hardly seventeen years old, it becomes difficult for me to live with my stepfather. So I left house, now I was standing on two paths I knew that one will take me to hell, while other one will lead to a respected life, I selected second one for me. It was very difficult journey but I have managed to live with respect. I was very sharp I always try to learn new things, when my mother was alive I did few courses during that period I did a beautician's course, cooking course, I also learned classical dance. So after living my stepfather's house I started doing performances at family functions. Initially I used to wear female dress but then someone told me that I should dance without costumes and I did so and started earning with respect as an artist, I have performed at regional and international level once I had performed in India, I am expert in cooking.

Implications of Study

The purpose behind selecting this topic was to explore the rich culture and social organization of third genders, this research will help to understand and separate the myths and actual practices of the third genders, this has also focused on the attitudes of people towards third genders, people often want to make distance from them without knowing them, and even don't try to know them at all, because there are several misunderstandings about third gender in our society this study also has focused on the traditional ways of bread earnings and challenges they are facing for earning, what are the risk and opportunities they have in our society? This study will help people to understand life of those who are living at the margins of society.

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Conclusion

This study is based upon first hand data collected through participant observation, interviews and direct discussions with third gender community, the study discloses the internal social structure of third gender community, and also explains that how that structure functions for the survival of individual and group life of community, how they are divided into categories on the basis of their biological variations and according to their caste.

They earn their living mostly by three ways i.e. as a dancer, begging at shops and by doing their traditional work of performing *Badhai* when a male child is born, they bless new born baby and receive donations from family, while majority of third gender community is engaged in prostitution, because usually *Badhai* is collected by inborn hermaphrodites, and emasculated members of community, transvestite earns through dance at functions, begging and prostitutions, their age and physical appearance decides that what work is beneficial for them, usually new teenager members of community prefer to have dance profession, but very limited become successful dancers, mostly middle aged transvestites are engaged in prostitution, and in old age they start begging at shops, but this classification can't be generalized because many of them do all three jobs at same time, some do begging and prostitution, other may do dance and prostitution.

Third gender community faces discrimination everywhere, it starts from their own family and remain continuous throughout their life, in society they are treated as alien people don't allow them to live as a common member of society, they always hurt them by discriminatory behavior with them on the basis of their gender, without knowing their condition, either they are facing any psychological disorder or they are biologically disabled by birth.

Third gender community have developed their tools and techniques for their survival in society, they have their unique norms and value system which bounds community with each other, their internal relations are based on mutual understanding and trust. There are different rumors about third gender community's belief system, many people thought that they take their dead bodies at night and buried it without any ritual prayers, but during my research I find this is not true, all my informants told that usually they go back to their families whenever they become critically ill, or in old age, but if they don't have any contact with their family, then their neighbors will arrange burial for them, they call a *Molvi* for *Gosal* and *Janaz-e-Nimaz*.

Third gender community has their own traditions which support their survival; they do make fictive relations with each other, as they can get help from their fictive relatives during hard times, they make *Geryas* for their social support and economical benefits, this practice also satisfy their desire of having husband like ordinary women. They have their own justice system which runs through *Chatai* they can call *Chatai* for any dispute, they never go to visit police for their inter community issues.

During this research I observed that they are very much kind and hospitable, when ever any of their community member visits them they always tried to nourish their guests whatever they can afford, during research I took my lunch regularly with them, I find them very humble and caring, usually they bless me by putting their hands on my head. Usually they all argued that people should consider them as human being, give them respect and should not humiliate them just because of their gender which is beyond their control.

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